

Supplementary Information for

Physiological, biochemical and genome-wide expression patterns during graded normobaric hypoxia in healthy individuals

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Supplemental Figures

Figure S1: Top 10 correlated genes with SpO₂ (Upregulated): Since SpO₂ went down significantly post-hypoxia, more abs Δ SpO₂ means more decline in SpO₂ in that individual. Upregulation of these genes, such as CYBB, CDKN1C, and HNRPUL1 during hypoxia, was seen to be correlated (negative) with less decline in SpO₂.

Figure S2: Top 10 correlated genes with SpO₂ (Downregulated): Since SpO₂ went down significantly post-hypoxia, more abs Δ SpO₂ means more decline in SpO₂ in that individual. Downregulation of these genes, such as DNANJA1, CKLF, and PARK7 during hypoxia, was seen to be correlated (negative) with less decline in SpO₂. Genes such as DDR1 was seen to be correlated (positive) with more decline in SpO₂. i.e. more downregulation, more decline in SpO₂.

Figure S3: Top 10 correlated genes with Heart Rate (Upregulated) Since Heart Rate (HR) went high significantly post-hypoxia, more abs Heart Rate means more rise in HR in that individual. Upregulation of these genes, such as SLC40A1, LBR, GNG2, and BIN2 during hypoxia, was seen to be correlated (positive) with rise in HR.

Figure S4: Top 10 correlated genes with Heart Rate (Downregulated) Since Heart Rate (HR) went high significantly post-hypoxia, more abs Heart Rate means more rise in HR in that individual. Downregulation of these genes, such as DDR1, ACTRT1, and MED22 during hypoxia, was seen to be correlated (positive) with a rise in HR. Genes such as CKLF and RNU1A3 were seen to be correlated (negative) with a lower rise in HR. i.e., more downregulation results in a lesser rise in HR.

Figure S5: Top 10 correlated genes with the Average RR intervals (Upregulated) Since the Average RR intervals went down significantly post-hypoxia, more abs Δ Average RR intervals means more decline in overall HRV in that individual. Upregulation of these genes, such as RTN4, LBR, and SULF2 during hypoxia, was seen to be correlated (positive) with a high decline in Average RR interval. Genes such as CYBB during hypoxia were seen to correlate (negative) with a lower decline in the Average RR intervals.

Figure S6: Top 10 correlated genes with the Average RR intervals (Downregulated): Since the Average RR intervals went down significantly post-hypoxia, more abs Δ Average RR intervals means more decline in overall HRV in that individual. Downregulation of these genes, such as RNU1F1, IDS, and ARID4B during hypoxia, was seen to be correlated (negative) with less decline in Average RR intervals.

Figure S7: Top 10 correlated genes with the RMSSD (Upregulated) Since the RMSSD went down significantly post-hypoxia, more abs Δ RMSSD means more parasympathetic decline in that individual. Upregulation of these genes, such as LBR and SLC40A1 during hypoxia, was seen to be correlated (positive) with a high decline in the RMSSD. Genes such as CDKN1C during hypoxia were seen to correlate (negative) with a lower decline in the RMSSD.

Figure S8: Top 10 correlated genes with the RMSSD (Downregulated) Since the RMSSD went down significantly post-hypoxia, more abs Δ RMSSD means more parasympathetic decline in that individual. Downregulation of these genes, such as DDR1, CKLF, and DNAJA1 during hypoxia, was seen to be correlated (positive) with more decline in the RMSSD. Genes such as PARK7 and SNORA12 during hypoxia were seen to be correlated (negative) with less decline in RMSSD.

Figure S9: Top 10 correlated genes with the HF Power (Upregulated) Since the HF power went down significantly post-hypoxia, more abs Δ HF power means more parasympathetic decline in that individual. Upregulation of these genes, such as CAST, GNG2, HIF1A during hypoxia, was seen to be correlated (positive) with a high decline in the HF. Genes such as RTN4 during hypoxia were seen to correlate (negative) with a lower decline in the HF power.

Figure S10: Top 10 correlated genes with the HF Power (Downregulated) Since the HF power went down significantly post-hypoxia, more abs Δ HF power means more parasympathetic decline in that individual. Downregulation of these genes, such as DDR1, MED22, and FGF23 during hypoxia, was seen to be correlated (positive) with more decline in the HF power. Genes such as CKLF and COX5B during hypoxia were seen to be correlated (negative) with less decline in RMSSD.

Figure S11: Top 10 correlated genes with the LF/HF (Upregulated) Since the LF/HF ratio went high significantly post-hypoxia, more abs LF/HF means more rise in the LF/HF ratio in that individual. Upregulation of these genes, such as EPB41, PRKCB1, CAST, LILRB2, and SELL during hypoxia, was seen to be correlated (positive) with a rise in the LF/HF ratio.

Figure S12: Top 10 correlated genes with the LF/HF (Downregulated) Since the LF/HF ratio went high significantly post-hypoxia, more abs LF/HF means more rise in the LF/HF ratio in that individual. Downregulation of these genes, such as BST2 and IL11RA during hypoxia, was seen to be correlated (positive) with a rise in the LF/HF ratio, i.e. more downregulation of these genes, more rise in LF/HF ratio.